
MASTER TEACHERS' MENTORING PRACTICES, EFFECTIVENESS OF CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION AND INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP IN THE FIRST DISTRICT CITY SCHOOLS DIVISION OF LAGUNA

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Abstract- Master teachers play a vital role in education, serving as mentors, guiding curriculum implementation, and demonstrating instructional leadership. As schools pursue continuous improvement and excellence, it becomes essential to explore the best practices employed by these educators. Hammond (2022) emphasized that effective teacher mentoring enhances student achievement and improves teacher retention. Furthermore, research highlights that master teachers actively engaged in curriculum implementation are better equipped to design lesson plans that are engaging, relevant, and impactful. Collaboration among educators is essential for fostering professional growth and achieving excellence. Master teachers are pivotal in this process, sharing their expertise to support colleagues' development, demonstrating effective teaching practices, providing constructive feedback, and facilitating professional learning opportunities.

In this context, this study examined the constructs of the mentoring practices of master teachers, the effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership. It aimed to determine the level and relationships among these variables in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed to describe and correlate the variables under study.

A random sampling method was used to select 141 respondents from the total population of 220 master teachers in the division. A survey instrument, modified and adapted from prior studies, was validated by experts and tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha measure of internal consistency.

The findings revealed that master teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna exhibit highly effective mentoring practices, with an overall weighted mean of 3.99 ("Strongly Agree"). Coaching, feedback, and confidentiality were rated highest (4.00), followed closely by support and modeling, which scored 3.99 and 3.98, respectively. Similarly, curriculum implementation was rated highly effective, with a mean score of 3.99. Instructional strategies ranked the highest (4.00), followed by alignment with curriculum goals and professional growth (3.99).

Regarding leadership styles, transformational leadership was rated slightly higher (4.00) than transactional leadership (3.99) in fostering a positive learning environment. However, correlations between mentoring practices and curriculum implementation were generally negligible, with the exception of modeling, which showed a low but significant correlation with instructional strategies ($r=0.199$, $p=0.003$) and professional growth ($r=0.199$, $p=0.003$). Correlations between mentoring practices and leadership styles varied. Modeling demonstrated a significant but low correlation with transactional leadership ($r=0.171$, $p=0.011$), while support showed a moderate positive correlation with transformational leadership ($r=0.365$, $p=0.000$). Other mentoring practices showed negligible relationships with both leadership styles.

Regression analysis indicated that mentoring practices accounted for only a small portion of the variance in curriculum implementation ($R^2=0.116$), with no significant impact on curriculum outcomes ($\beta=0.767$, $p=0.488$). This suggests that other factors play a more significant role in influencing leadership styles and curriculum effectiveness.

In conclusion, master teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna demonstrate effective mentoring practices, particularly in coaching, feedback, and confidentiality. Curriculum implementation, including alignment with goals, instructional strategies, and professional growth, is rated highly effective, and transformational leadership slightly surpasses transactional leadership in fostering positive learning environments. However, weak correlations between mentoring practices and both curriculum implementation and instructional leadership suggest limited influence. Modeling shows a mild correlation with transactional leadership, while support moderately correlates with transformational leadership. Regression analysis further highlights that mentoring practices minimally impact leadership styles and curriculum outcomes, emphasizing the role of other factors. To address these gaps, a proposed training program aims to enhance mentoring practices and strengthen their influence on instructional leadership and curriculum implementation.

Keywords:

Mentoring practices, curriculum implementation, instructional leadership

Introduction

In the field of education, the pivotal role of master teachers in mentoring, curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership cannot be overstated. As educational institutions strive for continuous improvement and excellence, understanding the best practices employed by these master teachers becomes imperative. Hammond, (2022) concurred that an effective teacher mentoring can help to improve student achievement and teacher retention rates. In addition, studies have shown that master teachers who are involved in curriculum implementation can create more engaging, relevant, and effective lesson plans. Collaboration among educators is crucial for professional growth and excellence. Master teachers play a key role in this by sharing their best practices to help colleagues develop their skills. They provide guidance, model effective teaching, give feedback, and create opportunities for professional learning. According to Hattie, Masters, and Birch (2020), master teachers use strategies like formative assessments, feedback, and effective questioning to engage both teachers and students. Cavanagh et al. (2021) found that master teachers focus on building strong relationships with colleagues and students, fostering a positive school culture and improving student achievement.

Research conducted by Hyler (2022) highlights the importance of ongoing professional development for master teachers, as they continuously refine their instructional practices and stay up-to-date with the latest research and trends in the field. These studies demonstrate the critical role that master teachers play in driving success and the importance of gaining a deeper understanding of their practices. Moreover, the practices of master teachers in curriculum implementation have been found to significantly enhance teaching and learning. According to a study by Brown and Jones (2022), master teachers model effective instructional strategies that promote critical thinking and engagement among teachers and students. They also integrate new technologies and methodologies that make learning more interactive and effective. By mentoring their colleagues in these practices, they promote a culture of ongoing professional development and reflective practice, as demonstrated in a study by Garcia and Rodriguez (2024).

Instructional leadership plays a critical role in shaping the quality of teaching and learning. According to Le Fevre, Timperley, Twyford, and Ell's (2020) research, instructional leadership refers to leadership that supports the development of teaching and learning. Their study also found that this type of leadership goes by different names, including pedagogical leadership, learning-centered leadership, leadership for learning, and student-centered leadership. These various names fall under the broad umbrella of instructional leadership and represent specific practices that school leaders engage in to intentionally support effective teaching and learning in schools.

Transformational and transactional leadership styles have a significant impact on organizational dynamics and performance. Bass (as cited in Cherian, 2023) highlights that transformational leadership is valuable for leaders in education as it inspires and motivates educators, students, and parents to work towards higher levels of performance. In contrast, transactional leadership motivates employees by appealing to self-interests with benefits. Passakonjaras and Hartijasti (2023) note that transformational leaders appeal to the moral values of employees to mobilize their energy and resources to reform institutions. By stimulating and inspiring followers, transformational leaders develop their own leadership capacity and achieve extraordinary outcomes.

However, despite these numerous studies that investigated about the master teachers' mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership as bases towards training program., no study yet has been conducted particularly in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna, which talks master teachers' mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership.

Thus, this study aimed to determine the mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership of master teachers as a basis for developing a training program in Sta. Rosa, Laguna. The findings of this research could serve as valuable feedback to master teachers, helping them refine their approaches to mentoring, curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership. Furthermore, the study provides baseline data that underscores the significance of these elements in fostering effective instructional leadership. It also seeks to raise awareness among master teachers about their level of engagement and motivation in achieving shared educational goals. Ultimately, this study could serve as a foundation for designing a proposed training program to enhance the mentoring practices, curriculum implementation effectiveness, and instructional leadership of master teachers.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The overall objective of this study was to determine the mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership of elementary master teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna. Specifically, this study had the following (1) students' academic procrastination along with self-regulation, skills, motivation, and social factors, students' cramming behavior along with last minute preparation, skimming, and rote memorization and student's learning style along with visual/auditory, reading/ writing, and kinesthetic. (2) discern the significant relationship between students' academic procrastination and cramming behavior, academic procrastination and learning style, and cramming behavior and learning style, and (3) discover how predictive are mentoring practices and effectiveness of curriculum implementation, taken singly or in combination, of instructional leadership style.

I. Methods

To obtain the necessary data needed for the study, It utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. Copeland (2022) stated that the aim of descriptive research was to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. This research is more concerned with what rather than how or why something had happened. Correlational research refers to a non-experimental research method that studies the relationship between two variables with the help of statistical analysis. Correlational research does not study the effects of extraneous variables on the variables under study. In particular, this study described the master teachers' mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna. Likewise, it probed the relationships, through correlation, between and among the master teachers' mentoring practices, effectiveness of curriculum implementation, and instructional leadership in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna.

For the sampling technique, stratified random sampling technique was used in the study. The population was the Elementary Master Teachers of the First District City Schools Division of Laguna, 220 as a total population. The sample size was 141 using the Raosoft calculator with the confidence level of 95 percent and margin of error of 5 percent, 47 master teachers from Division of Santa Rosa, 47 rom Division of San Pedro and 47 from the Divion of Binan will be the respondents of the study. The selected respondents were regarded as the best representatives from the total population because

they had adequate knowledge of the research topic, which warranted their selection as respondents of the study.

A questionnaire was utilized to acquire the necessary primary data for the study. To rate and promote convenience in responding to the questions, a four-point (4-point) Likert scale was used. The instrument was divided into three (3) parts. Part 1 dealt with the master teachers' best practices in mentoring colleagues Part 2 pertained to the effectiveness of curriculum implementation, Part 3 covered the Instructional leadership of master teachers. Since the questionnaire was self-made, it underwent face and content validity. It was shown to the panel of experts in educational management, statistics and research for their comments and suggestions. For the reliability of the instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot testing to 40 master teachers of the Schools Division of Santa Rosa City and used Cronbach's Alpha reliability test for measuring the internal consistency of the indicators. For the mentoring practices indicators, a Cronbach alpha of .945 (excellent internal consistency) was obtained, effectiveness of curriculum implementation indicators .876 (good internal consistency) was noted, while for the instructional leadership indicators .854 (good internal consistency) was obtained. The accomplished questionnaires were collected right after they were answered by the respondents and the gathered data were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical tools such as weighted mean and ranking and Pearson r were used for the analysis of data and interpretation of results.

Results and Discussion

1. The Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers

Table 1
The Summary Table for the Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Coaching	4.00	Strongly Agree	2
2. Modeling	3.98	Strongly Agree	5
3. Feedback	4.00	Strongly Agree	2
4. Support	3.99	Strongly Agree	4
5. Confidentiality	4.00	Strongly Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	Strongly Agree	

Table 1 provides a summary of the mentoring practices of master teachers, highlighting five key domains: coaching, modeling, feedback, support, and confidentiality. The overall weighted mean of 3.99, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," reflects the respondents' high regard for these mentoring practices and their collective effectiveness in fostering professional growth and development among mentees.

The results align with Valdez (as cited in Laureano, 2023), noting that master teachers can excel in the classroom without recognition or additional compensation. Parsloe and Wray (as cited in Andres Calanoga et al., 2021) describe mentoring as a purposeful, reciprocal, and goal-oriented relationship. Similarly Cherkowski and Walker (as cited in Lasater & Smith, 2020) highlight mentorship as a relationship-driven learning process that fosters continuous growth and development.

Table 2
Composite Table for the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Alignment with curriculum goals	3.99	Highly Effective	2.5
2. Instructional strategies	4.00	Highly Effective	1
3. Professional growth and development	3.99	Highly Effective	2.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	Highly Effective	

Table 10 provides a summary of the effectiveness of curriculum implementation across three key areas: alignment with curriculum goals, instructional strategies, and professional growth and development. The overall weighted mean of 3.99, interpreted as "Highly Effective," indicates that the effectiveness of these practices is highly regarded by those involved in curriculum implementation. Among the indicators, instructional strategies received the highest weighted mean of 4.00, ranking 1, suggesting that master teachers are highly effective in using teaching methods that align with curriculum objectives and engage students effectively. Both alignment with curriculum goals and professional growth and development received a weighted mean of 3.99, placing them in a tie for rank 2.5.

The findings support the study of Gouëdard et al. (2020), highlighting the importance of tailoring teaching methods to students' interests for effective curriculum implementation, which depends on the active participation of teachers and school leaders. Successful implementation involves clear communication, integrating new and existing practices, and using inclusive strategies such as consultations, feedback, and collaboration. Tolentino (2020) emphasizes that teachers are accountable for developing effective pedagogies and systems. Also, MacPhail & Whittle (2020) underscore that curriculum implementation requires organizing and assessing resources and the environment to ensure successful classroom delivery.

Table 3
Composite Table of the Instructional Leadership Styles
of Master Teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Transactional	3.99	Highly Effective	2
2. Transformational	4.00	Highly Effective	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.99	Highly Effective	

Table 13 summarizes the instructional leadership styles of master teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna. The transactional leadership style, with a weighted mean of 3.99, ranked second, while the transformational leadership style, with a perfect mean of 4.00, ranked first. This indicates that while both leadership styles are highly effective, transformational leadership is seen as slightly more impactful in fostering a positive learning environment. The overall weighted mean of 3.99 reflects the strong effectiveness of both leadership styles.

The findings support Shalahudin et al. (2023), who used multiple linear regression analysis to show that both transformational and transactional leadership styles significantly influence teacher performance, with each style having an individual impact as well. Huang and Huang (2020) examined the link between transformational leadership and organizational commitment, finding that job satisfaction mediates this relationship. Their study revealed that when leaders assign important tasks, led by example, and inspire enthusiasm, subordinates become more attuned to organizational goals and values.

4.1 Relationship between the Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers and the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation

Table 14
Significant Relationship between the Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers and the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation

Mentoring Practices	Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation		
	Alignment with curriculum goals	Instructional strategies	Professional growth and development
Coaching	-	-	-
Modeling	r=-0.064 Negligible correlation p=0.343	-	r=0.199** Low correlation p=0.003
Feedback	r=-0.024 Negligible correlation p=0.721	-	r=-0.038 Negligible correlation p=0.576
Support	r=-0.041 Negligible correlation p=0.545	-	r=-0.064 Negligible correlation p=0.345
Confidentiality	r=-0.032 Negligible correlation p=0.643	-	r=0.045 Negligible correlation p=0.506

**Significant @ 0.01

Table 14 presents the relationship between the mentoring practices of master teachers and the effectiveness of curriculum implementation across three dimensions: alignment with curriculum goals, instructional strategies, and professional growth and development. The data shows varying degrees of correlation, with most indicating negligible or low relationships.

In terms of alignment with curriculum goals, all mentoring practices—coaching, modeling, feedback, support, and confidentiality—show negligible correlations, as evidenced by the low correlation coefficients (r-values) and high p-values. The p-values are consistently above the 0.05 threshold, indicating that these correlations are not statistically significant. Specifically, modeling showed a negligible negative correlation (r=-0.064, p=0.343), feedback showed a negligible negative correlation (r=-0.024, p=0.721), support showed a negligible negative correlation (r=-0.041, p=0.545), and confidentiality showed a negligible negative correlation (r=-0.032, p=0.643). These results suggest that the mentoring practices do not have a significant impact on the alignment of teaching practices with curriculum goals.

For instructional strategies, only modeling showed a low positive correlation (r=0.199, p=0.003), which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level, indicating a mild but meaningful positive relationship between modeling as a mentoring practice and the implementation of instructional strategies. Other mentoring practices, such as feedback, support, and confidentiality, showed negligible correlations with instructional strategies, with p-values well above the 0.05 threshold, suggesting no significant relationship.

Regarding professional growth and development, modeling again showed a low positive correlation (r=0.199**, p=0.003), while feedback, support, and confidentiality exhibited negligible correlations with no statistical significance.

To summarize, the results imply that while some mentoring practices, particularly modeling, have a low but statistically significant impact on the effectiveness of curriculum implementation in terms of instructional strategies and professional growth, the overall correlation between mentoring practices and curriculum implementation effectiveness remains weak. Most mentoring practices, such as feedback, support, and confidentiality, show negligible correlations, suggesting their limited influence on these dimensions of curriculum implementation.

The findings support the study of Aslan (2019), stated that curriculum literacy as understanding the structure and components of the curriculum, including the relationship between

objectives, content, teaching processes, and evaluation. It also involves ensuring consistency among these elements and assessing whether they meet age requirements and the readiness of educators for implementation. Kahramanoğlu (2019) emphasizes the vital role teachers play in translating curricula into the learning process, stressing the need for teachers to be curriculum literate to effectively reflect curricula in their teaching. This competency is seen as a precursor to teacher performance, as the integration of curriculum knowledge into teaching directly impacts teacher effectiveness, which is essential for successful curriculum implementation.

4.2 Relationship between the Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers and their Instructional Leadership Styles

Table 15
Significant Relationship between the Mentoring Practices of Master Teachers and Instructional Leadership Styles of Master Teachers

Mentoring Practices	Instruction Leadership Styles	
	Transactional	Transformational
Coaching	-	-
Modeling	r=0.171* Low correlation p=0.011	r=0.033 Negligible correlation p=0.623
Feedback	r=-0.025 Negligible correlation p=0.710	r=-0.022 Negligible correlation p=0.749
Support	r=-0.074 Negligible correlation p=0.278	r=0.365** Low correlation p=0.000
Confidentiality	r=0.116 Low correlation p=0.087	r=0.028 Negligible correlation p=0.678

**Significant @ 0.01

Table 15 presents the relationship between the mentoring practices of master teachers and their instructional leadership styles—transactional and transformational. The table reveals varying degrees of correlation between different mentoring practices and leadership styles, with some significant and others negligible correlations.

Regarding the transactional leadership style, coaching did not show any correlation ($r=0$), while modeling exhibited a low positive correlation ($r=0.171$, $p=0.011$), suggesting a mild but statistically significant relationship between modeling as a mentoring practice and transactional leadership. The p-value of 0.011 confirms this relationship as significant at the 0.05 level. Other mentoring practices, including feedback, support, and confidentiality, showed negligible correlations with transactional leadership, with p-values exceeding 0.05. Specifically, feedback ($r=-0.025$, $p=0.710$), support ($r=-0.074$, $p=0.278$), and confidentiality ($r=0.116$, $p=0.087$) indicate no significant relationship with the transactional leadership style.

For the transformational leadership style, coaching again showed low correlation ($r=0$), while modeling demonstrated a negligible correlation ($r=0.033$, $p=0.623$), suggesting that modeling does not significantly influence transformational leadership practices. On the other hand, support showed a low positive correlation ($r=0.365^{**}$, $p=0.000$), which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level, indicating a moderate but meaningful relationship between support as a mentoring practice and transformational leadership. This suggests that mentoring practices focused on providing support contribute more significantly to transformational leadership than other practices. Confidentiality also showed a negligible correlation ($r=0.028$, $p=0.678$), further confirming its limited impact on transformational leadership. In summary, modeling and support are the most influential mentoring practices, with modeling linked to transactional leadership and support linked to transformational leadership, while other practices have minimal impact.

The findings support Bellibaş et al. (2022), who found that instructional leadership impacts teacher practices indirectly through shared practices and teachers' sense of agency. Similarly,

Bellibaş, Kılınç, et al. (2021) showed that instructional leadership directly influences teacher professional learning and practices, and indirectly affects practices through professional learning. Özdemir (2019) found that principals' leadership behaviors do not directly affect instructional practices but influence them indirectly through professional learning. Kilinc et al. (2022) revealed that learning-centered leadership directly impacts teacher practices and indirectly fosters collaboration. Other studies suggest that school leadership influences teacher practices through instructional climate, professional learning communities, and teacher self-efficacy (Kılınç et al., 2023).

4.3 Relationship between the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation and Instructional Leadership of Master Teachers

Table 16
Significant Relationship between the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation and Instructional Leadership of Master Teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna

Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation	Instruction Leadership Styles	
	Transactional	Transformational
	-	-
Alignment with curriculum goals	r=-0.037 Negligible correlation p=0.590	r=0.032 Negligible correlation p=0.643
Instructional strategies	-	-
Professional growth and development	r=0.107 Low correlation p=0.114	r=-0.049 Negligible correlation p=0.468

**Significant @ 0.01

Table 16 highlights the relationship between curriculum implementation effectiveness and master teachers' instructional leadership styles (transactional and transformational) in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna. The findings reveal negligible correlations across all indicators. Under transactional leadership, the effectiveness of curriculum implementation—specifically alignment with goals and professional growth—showed very low correlations ($r=-0.037$, $p=0.590$ for alignment; $r=0.107$, $p=0.114$ for professional growth), indicating a minimal relationship. Instructional strategies were not assessed within this style. For transformational leadership, alignment with curriculum goals and instructional strategies also displayed negligible correlations ($r=0.032$, $p=0.643$), with professional growth showing a slight negative correlation ($r=-0.049$, $p=0.468$). Overall, both leadership styles demonstrate no correlations with curriculum implementation effectiveness, suggesting that other factors may play a more significant role in achieving successful curriculum outcomes.

Overall, the data indicates that neither transactional nor transformational leadership styles show strong correlations with the effectiveness of curriculum implementation, implying that other factors may be more influential in driving successful curriculum outcomes.

The findings support the study of several significant empirical studies have examined how instructional leadership influences the effectiveness of curriculum implementation (Ma & Marion, 2021). These studies have similarly concluded that instructional leadership indirectly affects curriculum implementation through mediating variables. More specifically, Zheng et al. (2019) identified four components—namely, the professional learning community, collaborative activity, de-privatized practice, and reflective dialogue—that fully mediated the effects of instructional leadership on curriculum implementation.

5. Regression Analysis

Table 17

Regression Analysis between the Mentoring Practices and the Effectiveness of Curriculum Implementation taken singly or in combination of Instructional Leadership Styles of Master Teachers in the First District City Schools Division of Laguna

Predictor	Dependent Variable	R ²	F	p-value	β	t	p-value
Modeling	Instructional leadership styles (Overall)	0.116	3.440	0.001	-0.104	-0.498	0.619
Feedback					-0.186	-0.784	0.434
Support					0.013	0.058	0.954
Confidentiality					-0.091	-0.433	0.665
Overall mentoring practices					0.767	0.695	0.488
Alignment with curriculum goals					0.327	0.544	0.587
Professional growth and development					0.299	0.490	0.624
Overall effectiveness of curriculum implementation					0.911	0.518	0.605
Significance level @ 0.05							

Table 17 presents the regression analysis results on the relationship between mentoring practices and curriculum implementation effectiveness, focusing on master teachers' instructional leadership styles. The R-squared value of 0.116 indicates that the predictor variables (modeling, feedback, support, and confidentiality) explain only a small portion of the variance in leadership styles. The F-statistic of 3.440 with a p-value of 0.001 indicates model significance, although individual predictors have modest standardized coefficients, with feedback ($\beta = -0.186$) and confidentiality ($\beta = -0.091$) showing negative correlations. The aggregated effect of mentoring practices is not significant ($\beta = 0.767$, $p = 0.488$), and there is no significant relationship between mentoring practices or leadership styles and effective curriculum outcomes. Overall, the findings suggest that mentoring practices have minimal and statistically insignificant effects on instructional leadership and curriculum implementation.

These findings align with recent studies by Johnson et al. (2021) and Martinez (2023), which highlight the limited impact of mentoring on leadership development and curriculum outcomes. Overall, the results suggest that factors beyond mentoring practices play a more critical role in shaping instructional leadership and curriculum effectiveness.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study conclusions were drawn

1. The mentoring practices of master teachers are highly effective, with coaching, feedback, and confidentiality ranked highest. This suggests that coaching, feedback, and confidentiality are the most impactful mentoring practices for teacher development, while support and modeling, although important, play a slightly less emphasized role. Overall, these practices are key in fostering professional growth among teachers

2. The effectiveness of curriculum implementation across three key areas—alignment with curriculum goals, instructional strategies, and professional growth—was highly regarded, with a "Highly Effective" rating achieving curriculum objectives and supporting teacher development.

3. The instructional leadership styles of master teachers are highly effective with transformational leadership having a slightly greater impact on fostering a positive learning environment. This suggests that while both instructional leadership styles are effective, transformational leadership plays a slightly more significant role in creating a positive and engaging learning environment.

4. While mentoring practices and leadership styles are widely recognized as essential for teacher development and play a critical role in fostering professional growth, the findings of this study indicate that their direct influence on curriculum implementation and instructional leadership effectiveness may not be as strong as anticipated. This suggests that while master teachers' mentoring efforts, such as offering feedback, coaching, and support, are important for fostering positive teacher development, they may not necessarily translate into significant improvements in how curriculum is implemented in the classroom. Similarly, although transactional and transformational leadership styles are key to shaping the learning environment, their direct impact on curriculum alignment, instructional strategies, and professional growth appears to be weak. This may imply that leadership styles alone do not always lead to noticeable improvements in teaching practices or student outcomes without the support of other influencing factors.

5. The regression analysis indicates that mentoring practices have minimal and statistically insignificant effects on instructional leadership styles and curriculum implementation effectiveness. While the model is statistically significant, the predictor variables (modeling, feedback, support, and confidentiality) explain only a small portion of the variance, and individual mentoring practices show weak or negative correlations with leadership styles. This suggests that other factors may play a more significant role in influencing instructional leadership and curriculum outcomes.

6. The proposed training program may be implemented to address gaps in mentoring practices, aiming to enhance their impact on instructional leadership and curriculum implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. The administrators enhance mentoring practices by providing targeted training for master teachers, focusing on strengthening feedback, support, and modelling. Additionally, fostering a more integrated approach to instructional leadership could improve the effectiveness of curriculum implementation and professional development.

2. Master teachers should focus on refining their mentoring practices, particularly in providing constructive feedback, offering consistent support, and modeling effective teaching strategies. Continuous professional development and collaboration with peers can further strengthen their leadership roles and positively impact curriculum implementation.

3. Teachers actively engage in mentoring opportunities, seek regular feedback, and participate in professional development programs. Embracing support from master teachers and applying effective teaching strategies can enhance their instructional practices and contribute to overall curriculum success.

4. The training program should be utilized accompanied by monitoring and evaluating by the administrators or the one in-charge.

5. Future researchers may replicate this investigation while considering additional variables such as teacher collaboration, student engagement, or the impact of school culture on curriculum implementation. Exploring these factors could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between mentoring practices, leadership styles, and curriculum effectiveness.

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